

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Microbial contamination correlated to hygienic habits attitudes and practices toward handling contact lens units

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Abstract

Introduction: Contact lenses (CLs) are medical or cosmetic devices, comfortable and more convenient alternative to eyeglasses. Eye infection will result when microbes are introduced onto CLs, because defense against microbial invasion in the anterior chamber of the eyes is weak due to the very poor blood supply.

Method: The present study investigates hygienic habits, attitudes and practices of thirty CL wearers, toward lens care, that might yield to microbial contamination of CL units through examination of 120 samples (4 items of each CL units) to detect microbial growth and to understand associated factors through a structured questionnaire.

Results: Microbial contamination was detected in at least one item of twenty-five CL units (83.3%). None of disinfecting care solutions in original bottles was found contaminated. Incidence of microbial contamination in storage case (Right and Left) and rims of solution bottles was 21 (70%), 17 (56.7%) and 6 (20%) respectively. Eye redness after CLs wearing was almost a statistically significant sign associated with contaminated CL units ($p=0.088$). Using water only to wash hands and CL storage cases has been incriminated for increased contamination.

Conclusions: Impurities in CL storage cases have led to reduced efficacy of disinfectant care solutions. Value-added awareness of CL wearers should be improved by regular visit to eye care professionals.

Keywords: Contact lens units; Microbial Contamination; Hygienic Habits; Attitudes and Practices.

1 Introduction

Contact lenses are thin, light weight, almost invisible disks that serve as an excellent option and alternative to eyeglasses for people who need vision correction. Currently, ninety percent of contact lens wearers use soft contact lenses [1, 2] which were first introduced to the U.S. in 1971 [3]. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [4] have estimated that 45 million people in the U.S. wear CLs, two third of them are female with average age of 31 years. It is estimated that CL wearers are in excess of 150 million wearers [5]. The most common complications caused due to long term wearing CLs are minor including: discomfort, dryness and irritancy of eyes, burning when putting in lenses, allergy and physiological problems [6]. Fortunately, most problems are not serious and will resolve if the lens is removed for a period of time [7]. Major problems, although less common, but may be more dangerous for vision include: Conjunctive problems [8] particularly, allergic conjunctivitis [9] and Microbial Keratitis [10, 11] which may result in impaired vision [12] and deterioration of quality of life [13]. The eyes may get worse by different factors such as smoking, dust, air-conditioned rooms, and medication. Besides, wearing CL while sleeping have led to increased prevalence and severity of all complications especially the risk of Microbial Keratitis [6, 14].

Hygiene of CLs and their storage cases is necessary for safe wear, despite using disinfecting agent, CLs storage cases are the most alleageable item to get contamination [15,16] Commensals (Resident) and transient potential

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microorganisms (M.O) may approach lenses from wearer's fingers and eyelid edges while inserting lenses from CL storage cases, which in turn will be introduced to the disinfectant care solution resulting in decreased preservative efficacy; thereby, this solution will act as a good substrate for these microbes [17]. Accordingly, CLs acts as a vector to adhere to and transfer to the ocular surface resulting in inflammation or infection [18, 19, 20, 21, 22]

Disinfecting care solutions are improved over the years to become more efficient for surface cleaning and sterilization of CLs. It contains combinations of cleaning, disinfecting, moisturizing, and preventing of tear agents [23]. Yet, CL disinfecting care solutions with the same formulations, but manufactured by different companies, may possess different disinfecting potentials [24]. Besides, Dantam et al. [25] indicated that extent of microbial contamination of storage cases varies with the use of different formulations of CL care solutions.

Therefore, the aim of the present study is to investigate microbial contamination correlated to hygienic habits, attitudes and practices toward handling CL units.

2 Material and methods

Samples were collected through the period from October 2019 to March 2020. Participants are students currently wearing CLs (either long- lasting or daily use), randomly selected from colleges at Isra University aged >18 years. They signed the informed consent without any obligation; inquiries were answered and clarified at request. They were not taking any antibiotic nor eye medications [26] and no one was suffering from any eye disease, inflammation or infection at the time of sampling.

2.1. Questionnaire

Questions were constructed after searching through various articles [20, 26, 27, 28] and the part of questionnaire considering recommendations for CLs wearing was determined according to American Optometric Association [29]. Questionnaire included demographic data, eye-related health, personal hygienic habits, and CLs hygienic habits; some of which are close-ended and others are open-ended. No names were included in the survey and no financial reward was given.

2.2. Sampling

One hundred and twenty samples were taken from CL units of 30 participants. These included immersion disinfectant care solutions from: (1) Right and (2) Left CL Storage Case (RSC and LSC respectively), (3) disinfectant care solution from its original bottle and (4) swabbing mouth rims of disinfectant solution bottles.

Under sterile conditions, 0.5 ml immersion solutions from each RSC and LSC, from care solution and swabs were suspended in 4.5 ml Trypticase Soy Broth (TSB, biolab) containing 3% Tween 80 (Polysorbate 80) to neutralize the effect of disinfectant [30-31] then incubated at 35 °C for 1-2 hrs., to allow stressed microbial cells to recover. Two-fold dilutions of each sample (100 µL and 50 µL) were spread onto duplicate Trypticase Soy Agar (TSA, biolab) plates using sterile L-shaped solid glass rod (Dipped into spirit then flamed). Plates were incubated at 35 °C for 24-48 hrs. Growth of 10 or more bacterial colonies on plates was reported as contamination [30].

2.3. Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software version 25 for Windows. *p* value of equals or less than 0.05 was set as the significance level. Participant characteristics were reported by using means and standard deviations (SD) for continuous variables while frequencies with percentages were used for categorical variables. A dichotomous variable that represent bacterial isolate status was generated and was used to compare contaminated and non-contaminated samples using Chi square test (χ^2).

3 Results

Microbial contamination was detected in at least one item of twenty-five CL units (83.3%). None of disinfecting care solutions in original bottles was found contaminated. Incidence of microbial contamination in RSC and LSC and rims of solution bottles was 21 (70%), 17 (56.7%) and 6 (20%) respectively. Only one bottle rim was found contaminated (3.3%) without its storage case. Demographic characteristics as correlated to microbial contamination are illustrated in Table (1). A total of thirty CL wearers participated in the present study, all of them were females; age ranged between 19 - 36 years (\bar{x} = 23.5 years, SD \pm 3.2 years). The majority are undergraduate university students (86.7%), attending health-related colleges (63.3%) and studied a microbiology course (60%). All post graduate students are also studying

at health-related colleges. The overwhelming majority of participants are non-smokers (86.7%). Sixteen participants (53.3%) use CLs for cosmetic reasons while the remaining use CLs for medical reasons. Wearing CLs daily was associated with the least incidence of microbial contamination (72.7%) as compared to weekly (100%) or monthly (85.7%). Additionally, long-lasting CLs were the most popular type used (86.7%). Almost all participants (96.7%) are wearing CLs for at least one year.

Table 1 Demographics data of contact lens wearers

Demographic Data	Response	N=30 n (%)	Microbial contamination n =25 (%)	P-value
Health education*	Yes	19 (63.3%)	16 (84.2%)	0.865
	No	11 (36.7%)	9 (81.8%)	
Educational level	Undergraduates	26 (86.7%)	22 (84.6%)	0.631
	Post graduates	4 (13.3%)	3 (75.0%)	
Studied microbiology	Yes	18 (60%)	15 (83.3%)	1.000
	No	12 (40%)	10 (83.3%)	
CLs experience	≥ One year	29 (96.7%)	24 (82.8%)	0.649
	< Year	1 (3.3%)	1 (100%)	
Reason for wearing CLs	Cosmetic	16 (53.3%)	13 (81.3%)	0.743
	Medical	14 (46.7%)	12 (85.7%)	
Type of CLs	Long-lasting	26 (86.7 %)	21 (80.8%)	0.337
	Daily use (Disposable)	4 (13.3 %)	4 (100%)	
Smoking status	Yes	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	0.337
	No	26 (86.7%)	21 (80.8%)	
Frequency of wearing CLs	Daily	11 (36.7%)	8 (72.7%)	0.378
	Weekly	5 (16.7%)	5 (100%)	
	Monthly	14 (46.6%)	12 (85.7%)	
Periods of wearing CLs (hours)	1-4	6 (20%)	5 (83.3%)	0.071
	5-8	14 (46.7%)	11 (78.6%)	
	9-12	9 (30%)	9 (100%)	
	> 12	1 (3.3%)	-	

Table (2) demonstrates eye-related health status. Almost two-thirds (63.3%) of participants denied having any previous eye-related medical conditions/diseases. Nine out of eleven CL wearers (36.7%) had a previous eye-related conditions/disease and received medical examination. Diagnoses included: infection (n=4), inflammation (n=3) and dryness of eyes (n=2) where microbial contamination was detected at least in one item of CL units belonging to 2, 3 and 2 participants respectively. Reported conjunctivitis and keratitis were treated by antibiotics. None of the participants reported active eye infections at the time of the study. Eye redness after wearing CLs is almost significantly associated with microbial contamination of CL units. Also, CL units of wearers, continuously or intermittently suffering from eyelid boils, were found contaminated.

Table 2 Previous eye-related medical problems

Eye complications	Response	N=30 n (%)	Microbial contamination n =25 (%)	P-value
Eye medical condition / disease	Yes	11 (36.7%)	9 (81.8%)	0.865
	No	19 (63.3%)	16 (84.2)	
Eye redness after CL wearing	Always/Often	5 (16.6%)	5 (100%)	0.088
	Sometimes	18 (60%)	16 (88.9%)	
	Rarely/Never	7 (23.3%)	4 (57.1%)	
Eyelid boils	Always/Often	2 (6.7%)	2 (100%)	0.401
	Sometimes	5 (16.7%)	5 (100%)	
	Rarely/Never	23 (76.7%)	18 (78.3%)	

Most CL wearers (60%) have received instructions of CLs wearing and caring presented by health professionals. Participants were asked to evaluate their knowledge about instructions: eleven (36.7%) believed that their information regarding lens care is excellent, while 12 (40%) and 7 (23.3%) categorized their information as very good and good respectively. Twenty six (86.7%) are committed most often to instruction. Regardless of the degree of knowledge or commitment to instructions, microbial contamination was detected in at least one item of their CL units.

Table (3) demonstrates that most CL wearers (86.7%) do not require assistance for wearing CLs. All wearers wash their hands and dry them prior to CLs application, apart from four (13.3%) who do not dry their hands after washing. Microbial contamination appeared in CL units of wearers, who wash their hands only with water, and water or soap (alternatively). The majority (83%) avoided washing their faces with tap water while wearing CLs. Only one participant reported bathing/swimming while wearing CLs and another one shared his contact lenses with other person. Contact lens wearers who scarcely avoid touching their nails with CLs have 83.3% contamination in their CL units.

Contact lens wearers used two types of multipurpose solutions either included with the CLs when purchasing (53.3%) or use solutions commercially available in pharmacies (46.7%). Polyhexamethylene biguanide was the disinfecting agent in all solutions supplied with the CLs, though with different concentrations. The disinfecting agents of the trade names of solutions available in pharmacies are as following: solution A (Polyaminopropyl biguanide), solution B (Polyhexamethylene Biguanide) and solution C (Polyquaternium and Myristamidopropyl dimethylamine) which were used by 7 (23.3%), 6 (20%) and 1 (3.3%) participants respectively. Microbial contamination detected in CL units associated with solutions included with the CLs when purchasing was 13 (81.3%) and with types A, B and C were 6 (85.7%), 5 (83.3%) and 1 (100%) respectively.

Hygienic habits toward contact lenses and solutions are shown in Table (4). Few numbers of participants (10.0%) use a special plastic forceps to apply CLs. More than one half (56.7%) rinse their CLs with care solution, and only one third rub CLs while rinsing them. Rubbing lens with CL solution is significantly associated with microbial contamination of CL units. Eight participants (27.6%) reported using tap water instead of the recommended solution to store contact lenses at some points. Percentage of participants using water or using water and CL solution alternatively for washing CL storage cases was (38.9%) and (16.7%), respectively.

Table 3 Personal habits during wearing contact lenses

Personal habits	Response	N=30 n (%)	Microbial Contamination n=25 (%)	P-value
Personal use of CLs	Yes	29 (96.7%)	24 (82.8%)	0.649
	No	1 (3.3%)	1 (100%)	
Assistance required to wear CLs	Always/ Often	2 (6.7%)	1 (20%)	0.362
	Sometimes	2 (6.7%)	2 (100%)	
	Rarely/ Never	26 (86.7%)	22 (84.6%)	
Hand washing before wearing	Always/ Often	30 (100.0%)	25 (83.3%)	-
	Sometimes	-	-	
	Rarely/ Never	-	-	
Hand washing by:	Soap	22 (73.3%)	17 (77.3%)	0.336
	Water	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
	Soap or water (alternative)	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
Drying washed hand	Always/ Often	26 (86.7%)	21 (80.8%)	0.337
	Sometimes	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
	Rarely/ Never	-	-	
Avoiding touching CLs with fingernails	Always/ Often	8 (26.7%)	7 (87.5%)	0.861
	Sometimes	4 (13.3%)	3 (75%)	
	Rarely/ Never	18 (60.0%)	15 (83.3%)	
Sleeping while wearing CLs	Always/ Often	-	-	-
	Sometimes	-	-	
	Rarely/ Never	30 (100.0%)	25 (83.3%)	
Bathing or swimming while wearing CLs	Always/ Often	1 (3.3%)	-	0.023
	Sometimes	-	-	
	Rarely/ Never	29 (96.7%)	25 (86.2)	
Washing face while wearing CLs	Always/ Often	1 (3.3%)	-	0.061
	Sometimes	4 (13.3%)	3 (75%)	
	Rarely/ Never	25 (83.3%)	22 (88%)	
Avoiding smoking places while wearing CLs	Always/ Often	12 (40.0%)	10 (83.3%)	0.698
	Sometimes	8 (26.7%)	6 (75%)	
	Rarely/ Never	10 (33.3%)	9 (90%)	

Table 4 Hygienic habits toward contact lenses and solutions

Hygienic Habits	Responses	N= 30 (%) n (%)	Microbial Contamination n =25 (%)	P- value
Using forceps for wearing CLs	Yes	3 (10%)	2 (66.7%)	0.414
	No	27 (90%)	23 (85.2%)	
Rinsing lens with CL solution	Always/ Often	17 (56.7%)	14 (82.4%)	0.603
	Sometimes	9 (30%)	7 (77.8%)	
	Rarely/ Never	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
Rubbing lens with CL solution	Always/ Often	10 (33.3%)	8 (80%)	0.021
	Sometimes	6 (20%)	3 (50%)	
	Rarely/ Never	14 (46.7%)	14 (100%)	
Using water for CLs storage	Always/ Often	4 (13.8%)	4 (100%)	0.316
	Sometimes	4 (13.8%)	4 (100%)	
	Rarely/ Never	21 (72.4%)	16 (76.2%)	
Frequency of addition solution to CL storage cases	Daily	17 (56.7%)	14 (82.4%)	0.494
	Weakly	8 (26.7%)	6 (75%)	
	Monthly	5 (16.7%)	5 (100%)	
Frequency of washing CL storage cases	Always/ Often	18 (60%)	16 (88.9%)	0.157
	Sometimes	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
	Rarely/ Never	8 (26.7%)	5 (62.5%)	
Washing CL storage cases by:	Solution	12 (40%)	10 (83.3%)	0.845
	Water	11 (36.7%)	9 (81.8%)	
	Both	3 (10%)	3 (100%)	
	Not washing	4 (13.3%)	3 (75%)	
CLs storage cases replacement	Always/ Often	15 (50%)	12 (80%)	0.852
	Sometimes	6 (20%)	5 (83.3%)	
	Rarely/ Never	9 (30%)	8 (88.9%)	
Addition of residual old solution to the new one	Always/ Often	4 (13.3%)	3 (75%)	0.494
	Sometimes	1 (3.3%)	1 (100%)	
	Rarely/ Never	25 (83.3%)	21 (84%)	

Table (5) summarizes periods of using solutions and wearing lenses which was reported from the first date of commencement. Longer duration of CL care solutions usage is significantly associated with microbial contamination of CL units. More than one half (53.3%) had their contact lenses for more than one year. Only (50%) adhered to the manufacturer recommendations for proper use of CL care solution for less than 3 months. It should be noted that 45.5% of wearers use solutions for less than one month and use water when solution is not available.

Table 5 Duration of using disinfectant care solutions and contact lenses

CLs units	Duration Periods (Month)	N=30 n (%)	Microbial Contamination n =25 (%)	P-value
CLs Solution	<1	11 (36.7%)	10 (90.9%)	0.020
	1-3	4 (13.3%)	1 (25%)	
	4-6	2 (6.7%)	2 (100%)	
	7-12	4 (13.3%)	4 (100%)	
	> 12	9 (30.0%)	8 (88.9%)	
Contact lenses	< 1	3 (10.0%)	2 (66.7%)	0.105
	1-3	3 (10.0%)	3 (100%)	
	4-6	7 (23.3%)	7 (100%)	
	7-12	1 (3.3%)	-	
	>12	16 (53.3%)	13 (81.3%)	

4 Discussion

Wearing CLs is a main risk factor that may lead to sight threatening aggressive events mainly microbial keratitis. Personal attitude, hygienic habits and practices toward lens handling are believed to be significant sources of contamination. The present study showed that 80% of participants, wearing CLs for periods ranging from 5 to 12 hours daily, have their CL units contaminated, particularly, those wearing CLs for periods exceeding 9 hours. This is in accordance with the study conducted among Indian college students where 70% of those reporting problems related to the use CLs (e.g., foreign body sensation, dry eyes, and watering eyes), wear CLs for 8 to 16 hours daily [32]. Eye redness and dryness are also reported after wearing contaminated CLs which is in accordance with the symptoms of a case presented by McVeigh et al. [18] of a woman aged 21 year old from Singapore which used to wear CLs most of the day, sometimes sleep with them and clean them with tap water over two months.

Although 60% of CL wearers have received instructions from health professional for safe handling of CLs, 88.9% of their CLs units were found contaminated. This could be due to the quality of information received by lens wearers or poor commitment to the instructions. Lievens, et al. [33] indicated that education and compliance of CL wearers with hygiene habits are some of challenges facing care providers, where experience of wearers is not necessarily sufficient for commitment and protection from risks. Bakkar and Alzghoul [34] concluded that level of commitment is high towards four habits including: personal use of CL, not sleeping while wearing, hand washing before wearing and not using water to clean lenses. Level of commitment was medium to low towards the following habits: bathing or swimming while wearing CLs, using CLs and solutions after the expiry date, and rinsing CL storage cases and aftercare visits. These are almost in agreement with the participants' awareness in the present study.

Microbial contamination was higher in CL units of wearers washing their hands with water or soap alternatively as compared to those using soap always. Barlow et al. [35] concluded that using antibacterial liquid soap greatly inhibits microbial contamination in CLs compared to ordinary soap or using water only or those not washing their hands before wearing CLs.

Using water or solution mixed with water to wash CL units by some participants is in accordance with Zimmerman et al. [36] study who reported that many CLs wearers use tap water to wash CLs and CL storage cases. Microbial contamination by varied types of bacteria may result when using tap water, since it may contain dangerous microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Burkholderia cepacia*, and *Serratia marcescens* [37]. Besides, Shafqat, et al. [38] revealed the presence of Coliform group, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fecal *Streptococcus* in distribution systems of water. However, even distilled water if used to wash CL storage cases could be risky, because *P. aeruginosa* is able to grow relatively fast in distilled water, due to its very low nutritional requirement [39] and succeed to maintain high level contaminations for long periods of time. On the other hand, Wu et al. [40] applied different modes to wash lens storage cases using CL solutions and distilled water as a control. It should be noted that CLs solution remains the

most effective for cleaning, regardless of the washing method and type of solution, all solutions exert a significant effect in reducing biofilm formation compared to water ($P= 0.05$).

According to instructions of use labeled on the bottles of CL solutions, the solution should not be used for more than three months after opening. Statistically significant association was reported between duration periods of using solutions and microbial contamination in CL units ($p = 0.020$). The overwhelming majority of wearers are using solutions for more than three months and their associated units were found contaminated (Table 5). Nevertheless, contamination was also reported in 90% of CL units of wearers using solutions for less than one month, which may be due to the fact that almost one half (45.5%) of them use water when solution was not available. Dantam et al. [22] have reported a significant difference ($p = 0.013$) between bacteria contaminating CL storage cases using different CL solutions types.

Incidence of contamination of CL storage cases is greatly affected by the manner of handling each item of CL units. When solutions in CL storage cases, adhere to the lenses, they easily get contamination and become a source of microbes that cause infection of the cornea and inflammatory reaction [23]. Improper hygienic practices and failure of some preservative systems are implicated in the development of the contamination. When lens wearers use bared fingers during immersion of lenses or removal from the disinfecting care solutions; skin commensals, transient pathogens and faecal bacteria may stuck in CL storage case and subsequently can be transferred to the disinfectants. *Serratia* and *Pseudomonas* species are known for their resistance to some disinfecting solutions [41, 42]. Despite presence disinfecting agent, CL storage cases may not be completely free of contaminants, because some factors may lead consistent bacterial survival such as formation of biofilm. Although all solutions exert a significant effect in reducing biofilm formation [43], but when it is formed in CL storage cases, will protect bacteria and prevent disinfectant solution to reach it [15]. The other factor including selectivity for contamination with cytotoxic strains as *P. aeruginosa* [44]. Eltis [45] and Mohammadinia et al. [46] reported that 90% of the causative agent of microbial keratitis is *P. aeruginosa*, followed by *S. aureus*. Both of which are multidrug resistant and responsible for nosocomial infections.

In the present study, more than one half CL wearers use their storage cases for more than one year, where microbial contamination was reported, which is largely inconsistent with the FDA [47] recommendations. However, Kim et al. [48] did not find microbial contamination in all expired or nearly expired CLs.

Rims of solution bottles are the first point that disinfectant solution pass through before reaching CLs, also it may touch immersion care solution in CL storage cases. This was confirmed by the recovery of the same type of M.O in the rim of bottles as well as its CL storage case which is in accordance with Nzeako and Al-Sumri [24].

Strengths

- The study design included structured questionnaire tackling different aspects on attitude, practice and hygienic habits connected to handling of each item of CL units.
- The unique aspect of this study, there is no available literature on swabbing rims of solution bottles which provided valuable information on this topic.

Limitation

- Small sample size because of curfew.
- Only female participants were available.
- Direct eye swab was not included.

5 Conclusion

Using water only to wash hands and CL storage cases has been incriminated for increased contamination. Thereby, impurities in CL storage cases have led to reduced efficacy of disinfectant care solutions. Value-added awareness of CL wearers should be improved by regular visit to eye care professionals.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The research is a part of MSc. Thesis of the first author, there is completely no conflict of interest and no fund was received from any source. **If two or more authors have contributed in the manuscript, the conflict of interest statement must be inserted here.**

Statement of ethical approval

The study was conducted according to the standards set by Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as reviewed in 2008." Approval to commence the study was obtained from the Ethical Committee of Isra University (No. Ph/03/19).

Statement of informed consent

Filling out the survey was contingent upon the participants' sign the informed consent form attached to the actual survey.

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